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Faculty of Technology and Bionics

BACHELOR THESIS

*The German Research-Performing Pharmaceutical
Industry on Twitter*

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Abstract

Research-performing pharmaceutical companies have the expertise to share health information on social media. Examining their communication patterns and evaluating the subsequent results could assist them at generating more impact on such platforms. Also, little is known about how the Covid-19 pandemic outbreak affected discussions on social media about the broader pharmaceutical industry.

This research investigated how 10 randomly sampled German research-performing pharmaceutical companies utilized Twitter. The communication models, message functions, and organizational topics of their tweets (n = 1663) were determined in a deductive content analysis. It was found that certain types of tweets generally had significantly different metric-based impacts. A longitudinal sentiment analysis of tweets from German users about the broader pharmaceutical industry (n = 1755) shows that most of those tweets (63.2%) had a negative sentiment. Additionally, the structural characteristics “age” and “financial performance” of the sampled companies were juxtaposed with Twitter metrics such as their number of followers or their tweet frequencies. No significant associations were found.

This research concludes that GRPs have a monologue-based communication approach, and that they do not sufficiently capitalize on the interactive opportunities presented by Twitter which the research corpus considers to be pivotal for corporate communication and reputation management on social media. Moreover, the pharmaceutical industry is a controversial topic on German Twitter. The large number of negative sentiment tweets and the emotional involvement of a substantial proportion of critics may make it challenging to resolve those conflicts.

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List of abbreviations

GRP	German research-performing pharmaceutical
WHO	World Health Organization
R&D	Research and development
CSR	Corporate social responsibility
API	Application programming interface
MSD	Merck Sharp & Dohme
GSK	GlaxoSmithKline
BMS	Bristol-Myers Squibb
RQ	Research question

1.0 Introduction

Several scholars argue that it is imperative for any healthcare organization to engage with stakeholders on social media (e.g., Abroms et al. 2019; Park et al., 2016; Costa et al. 2018; Shankar & Li, 2014). In fact, a standardized nationwide survey suggests that 46% of Germans consult the internet to acquire health information (Marstedt, 2018, p.10). However, Shankar & Li (2014) pointed out that it was challenging to develop effective communication strategies because of regulations for pharmaceutical companies and difficulties in measuring the returns of investment of social media communication (pp.481-482). Finding solutions to these problems seems important considering that social media are permeated with misinformation (Del Vicario et al., 2016, p. 558). Reputation also plays a major role for pharmaceutical companies because they need to be recognized as providers of reliable health information if they want individuals to use that knowledge.

In a commentary, Kessel (2014) stated that citizens had perceived the pharmaceutical industry as more trustworthy before its reputation gradually worsened due to several reasons. For example, many executives had a history of prioritizing the needs of shareholders over those of patients (p. 984). Factors outside the control of pharmaceutical companies also contributed to the reputation decline. On the internet, for instance, the pharmaceutical industry was frequently inappropriately discredited (p. 985). However, the Covid-19 pandemic may have influenced how social media users perceive this industry at large, and individual pharmaceutical companies in particular.

Studying how pharmaceutical companies use Twitter could help them to identify weaknesses preventing them from generating more impact on those platforms. To better comprehend the status quo of their social media communication, their current communication patterns and the respective impacts should be examined. Corporate communication practitioners could then draw on the results of such research to assess and anticipate the outcomes of certain communication approaches on social media platforms.

1.1 Scope of this research

Borchelt (2014) distinguished between two levels of corporate communication impacts - that is, the program level (e.g., the number of likes, clicks, and shares received) and the organizational level (i.e., how well those social media activities help to achieve broader organizational goals). It would have gone beyond the scope of this research project to assess social media impacts on the organizational level because each pharmaceutical company can have different organizational goals. Communication impacts were therefore assessed on the program level only.

Furthermore, this study exclusively investigated companies involved in research and development of new pharmaceutical products (i.e., those not available yet on the market). By focusing on this part of the pharmaceutical industry, it was possible to compare the communication approaches of companies that were involved in research and development of Covid-19 vaccines with the communication approaches of companies that were not. To make an appropriate comparison, only posts since 04/13/2021, when GRPs were already in the process of researching or developing a Covid-19 vaccine were analyzed. On that date, the World Health Organization (WHO) made a public statement regarding collaboration for the development of Covid-19 vaccines (WHO, 2020a). This may have contributed to an increase in public attention towards Covid-19 vaccine development and research.

The microblogging platform Twitter was the only social medium analyzed in this study because it allows automatic scraping of publicly-available data without having to ask the respective users for admission (as is the case for Facebook, for example).

To avoid a mixed sample of companies operating under different regulatory environments, only research-performing companies that are present in the German market and attempt to communicate to a German audience on Twitter were sampled. For example, it is allowed to advertise prescription medicine directly to customers in the United States unlike in Canada where companies

face significant restrictions (Desiraju & Van Tran, 2014, p.674). The above specified types of companies will be henceforth referred to as “German research-performing pharmaceuticals” (GRPs).

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Research on the organizational use of Twitter

To investigate the organizational use of Twitter, studies can draw on quantitative data such as metrics and on qualitative data (i.e., the content of the tweets). Studies based on qualitative data have repeatedly concluded that organizations predominantly use Twitter to disseminate information rather than engaging in conversations (e.g., Lovejoy & Saxton, 2012; Park et al., 2016; Neiger et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2020).

Costa et al. (2018) who based their research entirely on quantitative data found that there were no significant associations between engagement on social media (Youtube, Facebook, and Twitter) and the size of pharmaceutical companies measured by the number of employees and financial revenue. To calculate engagement levels for Twitter accounts ($n = 20$), the sum of received mentions, retweets, and replies was divided by the number of followers (p.87). This formula did not disclose, however, whether engagement happened in a desired way because replies can have positive or negative sentiments. Costa et al. concluded that there were other factors influencing engagement on social media that should be investigated in further research.

To find certain communication patterns of organizations on social media, it is helpful to quantify the content they produce in content analyses. Lovejoy & Saxton (2012) claimed to be the first to develop categories for organizational messages on Twitter. Following their research, tweets could either have the purpose of disseminating information, engaging with a community, or encouraging others to perform certain actions (see table 1).

Table 1. Three message functions of tweets defined by Lovejoy and Saxton (2012).

Function	Definition
Information	“Spreading information about the organization, its activities, or anything of potential interest to followers.” (p. 341)
Community	“[...] foster relationships, create networks, and build communities on Twitter through tweets that promote interactivity and dialogue. The heart of this function are “dialogic” messages and those that attempt to build a community of followers via “bonding” messages, such as “thank you” and acknowledgement tweets.” (p.343)
Action	“[...]has as a central purpose the aim of getting followers to “do something” for the organization, whether it is to donate, buy a product, attend an event, join a movement, or launch a protest. Promotion and mobilization are at the heart of this function.” (p.343)

These categories were the result of an inductive content analysis of 2,437 tweets from 73 non-profit organizations. 56.6% of the tweets were coded as information-tweets, 25.8% as community-tweets, and 15.6% as action-tweets. Lovejoy & Saxton concluded that sending dialogic and community-building tweets was a more appropriate way of engaging with stakeholder on Twitter. It should be noted, however, that only 200 tweets were double-coded in this study. Nevertheless, a substantial amount of research has been based on

Lovejoy & Saxton's tweet classification scheme (e.g., Neiger et al., 2013; Park et al., 2016; Han et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2020; Slavik et al. 2021).

Neiger et al. (2013) analyzed the use of Twitter by local U.S health departments and found that they more often sent tweets about personal health ($n = 1628$) rather than about organizational matters ($n = 1186$). By categorizing those two groups of tweets with Lovejoy & Saxton's (2012) three message functions, they found that personal health was mostly communicated with information-tweets (58.5%). Likewise, information-tweets were also predominantly used to address organizational matters (51.9%). The authors argued that the frequent use of information-tweets was not appropriate because communication approaches based on information dissemination should be targeted to specific audiences which had to be identified first through dialogic communication. The results of their study seem to be reliable because each tweet was double coded and full consensus was reached.

Park et al. (2016) also distinguished between tweets about personal health and tweets about organizational matters and used Lovejoy & Saxton's (2012) three message functions to classify 1583 randomly sampled tweets from three major U.S health organizations. Unlike in the study by Neiger et al. (2013), the majority (67.7%) of the tweets were about organization-related matters and tweets about personal health constituted a smaller fraction of the sample (32.3%). Information-tweets ($n = 464$) were, again, used more often than action-tweets ($n = 46$) to communicate about personal health. The program-level impact of the message functions was also evaluated in this study. A significant interaction between the message function of tweets and the received number of retweets was detected ($p < 0.001$). In particular, tweets with personal health action-based messages received on average the most retweets. Notably, this tweet type constituted the smallest fraction of the sample (2.9%). Park et al. concluded that the organizations made insufficient attempts to create dialogic loops with their audience which the authors considered to be pivotal for organizations on Twitter (p.10). Also Thackeray (2012) said that effective health promotion comprised dialogic feedback loops on social media (p.168). Conversely, Lovejoy & Saxton (2012) considered the possibility that dialogic

communication was not necessarily the ideal form of organizational social media communication, but rather one key component thereof, and that it was not clear which combination of their three message functions was the most appropriate for each individual organization (p.349). When drawing on the results from Park et al.'s (2016) study, the following limitations should be considered: First, the three organizations were not equally represented in the sample. For example, the tweets from the American Heart Association constituted 50% of the sample, and the tweets from the American Cancer Society only 17.2%. Secondly, as in Lovejoy & Saxton's (2012) study, only the training data was double-coded.

Han et al. (2019) applied Lovejoy & Saxton's (2012) tweet classification scheme via automated text analysis in a health communication context. They distinguished between media and non-media Twitter accounts (i.e., accounts with many followers and accounts with few followers) and found that non-media accounts more often sent tweets encouraging health-improving actions, whereas media accounts focused on disseminating health information. Furthermore, "many health-related tweets" used the term "don't" (p.435). The authors posed the question whether the frequent use of negative expressions was appropriate in a health communication context. Issues regarding data accuracy were not addressed in this study as stated by the authors. Nevertheless, distinguishing between media and non-media accounts seems to be an insightful approach if these two types of Twitter accounts attract different types of audiences. It seems, however, that this has not been explored yet.

Slavik et al. (2021) found that tweets ($n = 501$) from Canadian public health agencies and decision makers ($n = 128$) in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic were more likely to be retweeted if they encouraged users to perform certain actions ($p < 0.001$). Notably, also Park et al. (2016) whose study was discussed above found that action-tweets from health organizations received significantly more retweets. Slavik et al. (2021) furthermore investigated their use of risk communication strategies. The most frequently employed strategy was to reference the abilities of individuals or communities to perform certain

actions that result in improved security correctly. However, the risk communication coding scheme only applied to 54% of the tweets in their sample. Also, only the training data was double-coded.

From the scholars mentioned above, Park et al. (2016) and Neiger et al. (2013) distinguished between tweets about personal health and tweets about organizational matters. It would be insightful to further explore which types of organizational topics are discussed in tweets. Via an inductive content analysis, Zhang et al. (2020) developed content categories for organizational tweets. Their coding scheme (see table 2) could be of value for research investigating how health organizations use Twitter. They also developed other categories which, however, do only seem to be applicable to companies involved in information technology.

Table 2. Definitions of the organizational topic categories developed by Zhang et al. (2020)

Organizational topic	Definition
Community relations	“...building relationships with stakeholders by sending greetings, offering entertaining items (e.g., quizzes and games), and promoting community activities...” (p.375)
Corporate social responsibility (CSR)	“...activities that go beyond the companies’ self-interest: for instance, removing barriers for disabled people, providing support for social equality and diversity, or protecting the environment.” (p.379-380)

Table 2. (continued)

Research & Development (R&D)	“...companies showcased their latest products and technologies or published research findings from their labs.” (p.380)
Business insights	“...companies shared business-related knowledge, such as how to improve customer loyalty or create brand awareness.” (p.380)
Partner relations	“...tweets about companies’ alliances and collaborations with other parties (e.g., joining other companies to establish a new company or introducing partners in manufacturing).” (p.380)
Human resources	“...focused on the companies as employers, providing information about recruitment and corporate working environments and sharing employees’ career experience.” (p.380)
Corporate achievements	“...noteworthy achievements, such as being recognized as most reputable company or getting a high score on relevant rankings.” (p.380)
Government relations	“...involved the companies’ public affairs efforts, informing people and influencing lawmakers about legislation and public policy.” (p.380)

From the topics listed in table 2, community relations, corporate social responsibility and research & development were addressed the most by the 10 information technology companies analyzed by Zhang et al. (2020). They also

used Lovejoy & Saxton's (2012) three message functions and found that those companies mostly sent information-tweets (53%) and rather infrequently sent community-tweets (n = 7%). Again, only the training data was double-coded.

Thus far in this literature review, most of the mentioned studies focused on distinguishing between dialogic and monologue-based communication approaches by health organizations on Twitter. However, there seems to be a further dimension across which the tweets of health organizations could be assessed, namely the usefulness of the information they provide. In fact, Lewis (2001) said that organizations were unlikely to affect individuals by only promoting their own agenda. Instead, they had to primarily address the agenda of their audience (p.31). In their four models of public relations, Grunig and Hunt (1984) distinguished between press agency and public information. The former could be regarded as an indicator for self-promotional tweets and the latter as a vague indicator for tweets with potentially useful information for individuals outside of the organization. Edman (2010) who used Grunig & Hunt's (1984) models to categorize 1577 tweets from 47 companies found that the press agency model (n = 533) was used more often than the public information model (n = 227).

Based on this literature review, it can be deduced that health organization's use of Twitter remains predominantly within the confines of information dissemination despite the higher effectiveness of dialogic and community-driven approaches at engaging and establishing relationships with stakeholders.

2.2 Corporate reputation on Twitter

"[...] in today's sensitive business milieu, a firm's ultimate survival may well depend on developing and maintaining a recognizable image and favorable reputation." This was already argued in 1998 by Gray & Balmer (p.695) when companies were not yet exposed to negative word of mouth by numerous users on platforms such as Twitter. Also Elkington (2013) said that certain companies disappeared because of societal value-based shifts. Social media in particular seem to play a vital role in the context of reputation management. In fact, Jones

et al. (2009) stated that comprehending how to manage the reputation of companies in online environments was becoming a key component of business (p.928).

The required research efforts seem to make reputation management a challenging task. For example, according to Bunting & Lipski (2000) reputation management involved understanding the presumptions and beliefs of stakeholders which seldom remained constant (p. 171). It is also important to study the relationships between certain social media communication approaches and the subsequent reputational changes (Floreddu et al., 2014). Moreover, the emergence of the internet significantly magnified the reach of word of mouth information-sharing (Becker et al., 2013). GRPs therefore need to monitor relevant social web environments, in particular because they are often inappropriately discredited on the internet (Kessel, 2014, p.985). Sentiment analysis is a method that can be used to follow whether social media users express positive, neutral, or negative sentiments towards certain companies or industries.

In a pioneering study, Jansen et al. (2009) conducted a sentiment analysis of 149,472 brand-related tweets collected over a time-frame of 13 weeks. They found that only a few of those tweets expressed negative sentiments (7.4%). However, the results of their study are primarily based on an automated sentiment analysis which has certain ramifications (see Jensen, 2017). Hornikx & Hendriks (2015) replicated their study with human coders and found that 44.13% of all sampled sentiment tweets (n = 639) were negative. However, Jansen et al. (2009) and Hornikx & Hendriks (2015) did not analyze sentiments towards the same brands, which decreases the comparability of the results from both studies.

Nevertheless, the fact that individuals use platforms like Twitter to express negative sentiments towards companies has several implications for GRPs. First, monitoring the social web could lead to insights about what individuals or certain groups dislike about pharmaceutical companies. Collecting data from social media to gain such insights also seems less expensive than e.g., conducting focus groups or interviews. On the other hand, identifying which

types of individuals or groups express certain viewpoints online seems challenging because users are not obligated to share personal details on their accounts. Second, users could spread rumors or mis- and disinformation about certain GRPs or the pharmaceutical industry at large. By proactively monitoring the social web environment and by anticipating such behavior from users, GRPs might reduce or prevent subsequent reputational damage. For example, Becker et al. (2013) referred to a video shared via YouTube that captured how food from Domino's Pizza had been served under deliberately unhygienic conditions (p.294). Had the company not publicly responded within a few days, the resulting reputational damage were probably more severe. However, a survey of 596 European public relations practitioners by Macnamara & Zerfass (2012) yielded that only 29 percent of them were monitoring social media. It would be insightful to conduct such a survey with corporate communications practitioners of GRPs to assess whether they invest sufficient effort into monitoring their reputation online.

In addition to potentially expensive investments in research, one critical impediment for companies to succeed in building and managing their online reputation seems to be the culture that has developed on the internet. Bunting & Lipski (2000) pointed out that the internet, or rather individuals on the internet fostered an "anti-corporate-culture" (p.173). They mentioned several drivers behind the strong prevalence of negative sentiments towards companies in the online realm. For instance, the internet gave rise to more convenient access to alternative sources of information that were often critical of corporations. Bunting & Lipski also pointed out that during the establishment of the internet, a "credibility-gap" between consumers and corporations had begun to grow due to disruptive events such as the effects of thalidomide (p.173). Taking these factors into consideration, it is not surprising that the integrity of companies is often questioned on the internet. However, it seems to be unclear how the online realm differs from the offline world. It could be the case, for instance, that users of the internet have a higher tendency to demonstrate hostility towards corporations when communicating online, and that they express more moderate viewpoints in offline settings. In fact, Jensen (2017) doubts the notion that the online world perfectly reflects offline reality. Although, in certain cases,

opinions expressed online might be more “real” because of the granted anonymity without which spiral-of-silence effects might prevent individuals from stating their true opinions (see Noelle-Neumann 1974).

From a corporate perspective, however, a striking feature of social media seems to be the empowerment of stakeholders to rapidly damage the reputation of companies (Floreddu et al., 2014, p.3). It therefore seems crucial for GRPs to gain or maintain a solid foothold in interactive online environments. Several scholars argued that certain communication patterns ought to be avoided to achieve that. For example, Jones et al. (2009) said that there was “little space for monologue” in the social web because community participation constituted a key component of reputation building (pp. 930-931). Also Gruber (2008) underscored that the social web was driven by collective participation of its users (p.1).

These statements coincide with those of the previously mentioned scholars who said that health organizations ought to employ more dialogic communication on social media (e.g., Lovejoy & Saxton, 2012; Park et al., 2016; Neiger et al., 2013). Consequently, GRPs would need to be open to unfamiliar viewpoints and “contend with the anarchy and diversity of the Net” (Bunting & Lipski, 2000, p.175).

3.0 Research questions (RQs)

RQ1: What types of tweets are sent how frequently by GRPs, with which impact on the program level?

RQ2: Which sentiments toward the broader pharmaceutical industry and individual GRPs can be deduced from the views expressed by German Twitter users?

RQ3: How do certain structural characteristics of GRPs correlate with their metrics, impacts, and communication behavior on Twitter?

3.1 Hypotheses

H1: GRPs involved in Covid-19 vaccination research or development focus on different organizational topics compared to uninvolved GRPs.

H2: Tweets by GRPs containing organization-related information generally receive less endorsement than tweets not about organizational matters.

H3: CSR and R&D are the most endorsed organizational topics by those who follow GRPs on Twitter.

H4: Tweets about CSR generally receive more positive replies when compared with tweets containing other organizational topics.

H5: GRPs predominantly communicate about health by disseminating information.

H6: Tweets that encourage health-improving actions generally receive more endorsement than tweets that disseminate health information.

H7: Objective communication by GRPs resonates more strongly with their Twitter followers rather than self-promotional tweets.

H8: Tweets with a two-way communication model are correlated with a higher number of replies compared to tweets with the communication model “press agency” or “public information”.

H9: R&D tweets are the most controversial (indicated by the number of negative replies).

H10: GRPs that are more interactive on Twitter are more likely to receive endorsement from other users.

H11: GRPs that are financially more successful (measured by their financial turnover in 2020) are more likely to be more active on Twitter (measured by their tweet frequencies).

H12: GRPs that are less active on Twitter (measured by their tweet frequencies) are more likely to have less followers.

H13: Older GRPs (measured by their age since foundation) are more likely to have a higher number of followers on Twitter.

H14: The number of tweets with positive sentiments increased after the UK authorized Covid-19 vaccines for public use.

H15: The number of tweets with negative sentiments increased after the announcement of the slow-down of the vaccine rollout.

H16: Tweets with negative sentiments towards the pharmaceutical industry were more likely to be emotional when compared to neutral and positive sentiments.

H17: The number of positive sentiment tweets increased after the declaration of the pandemic.

H18: Positive sentiment tweets generally received more endorsement compared to neutral and negative sentiment tweets.

4.0 Methodology

Three main types of analyses were conducted: A tweet categorization based on a deductive content analysis, a sentiment analysis based on a deductive and

partly inductive content analysis, and a structural analysis that was entirely based on quantitative data. The codebooks and the data are available on Zenodo (Bopp, 2022).

4.1 Sampling of GRPs

In order to gain a sample of GRPs, the vfa was used as a filter organization.

The vfa is a key organization in the German pharmaceutical market with its 47 member institutions involved in research and development (vfa, n.d.). The organization claims to seek dialogues with healthcare stakeholders and establish synergies between society and science.

19 of all vfa members had a German Twitter account and therefore qualified for being included in the sample. The account of a GRP was considered German if it used the German language or attempted to communicate with a German audience. If a GRP mostly communicated in English but made replies in German, retweeted or liked German tweets, and set Germany as the location of their account, we concluded that the account was attempting to communicate with a German audience.

There were several metrics based on which a sample could have been taken. However, we considered sampling based on the degree of activity of the Twitter accounts to be the most appropriate because that enabled a representative inclusion of different approaches to communication on Twitter. We used the tweet frequencies of the respective accounts as indicators of their degrees of activity which was calculated by dividing all tweets made by an account by the respective account age (in days). A simple random sample was taken by putting the names of the GRPs in a Google Sheets table and selecting the first 10 names after applying the “randomize range” - functionality.

Table 3. Tweet frequencies of all GRPs (sampled GRPs are highlighted).

GRP	Tweet frequency (in tweets/ day)
AbbVie	1,50
Amgen	0,79
Bayer	1,08
Biogen	0,49
BioNTech	0,15
Bristol-Myers Squibb (BMS)	0,46
Boehringer Ingelheim	0,96
Daiichi Sankyo	0,33
Fresenius	0,72
GlaxoSmithKline (GSK)	0,74
IDT	0,17
Janssen	1,45
Medigene	0,08
Merck	1,44
Minaris	0,39
Merck Sharp & Dohme (MSD)	1,59

Table 3. (continued)

Pfizer	2,73
Roche	0,97
Sanofi	0,98

With the formula below, we determined how many organizations should be sampled.

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \sigma^2}{e^2}$$

Equation 1. Sample size calculation with unit-based margin of error

We used the value 1.96 for Z to have a confidence interval of 95%. The margin of error (e) had to be a unit-based and not a percentage in this formula. We therefore had to make our own estimation of what an appropriate value was. Defining the margin of error as 0.4 tweets per day seemed reasonable because the tweet frequencies ranged from 0.8 to 2.73 tweets per day (see table 4). Unfortunately, no previous studies were found that took samples of organizations based on their social media metrics. The selection of the value for the margin of error could therefore not be based on prior studies.

The standard deviation (σ) was 0.63 tweets per day. This resulted in a sample size of 9.53 which was rounded up to 10.

4.2 Structural analysis

In the structural analysis, certain structural data from the sampled companies were juxtaposed with their Twitter metrics (Table 5). This part of our research was a conceptual replication of Costa et al. (2018).

4.2.1 Data collection

The data for the structural characteristics of the GRPs (table 4) were collected by means of desk research (dates of collection: 08/27/2021 – 08/30/2021). The Twitter metrics (table 5) were collected with the standard application programming interface (API) key provided by Twitter (date of collection: 08/20/2021).

Table 4. Structural data with references.

GRP	Market capitalization (in billions of Euros)	Financial performance in 2020 or 2019 (in billions of Euros)	Number of employees	Year of foundation and age	Involvement in Covid-19 vaccination research or development
Janssen	Could not be found	1.78 (D&B, n.d.)	40,000 (Janssen, n.d.-a)	1953 (Janssen, n.d.-a), 68 years	Involved (Janssen, n.d.-b)
Fresenius	23.02 MSN, n.d.-a)	36.2 (Fresenius, 2020)	311,269 (Fresenius, 2020)	1912 (Fresenius, n.d.), 109 years	Not involved
Daiichi Sankyo	39.8 (MSN, n.d.-b)	7.2 (Daiichi Sankyo, 2021)	16,033 (Daiichi Sankyo, n.d.-a)	2005 (Daiichi Sankyo, n.d.-b), 16 years	Involved (PipelineReview, 2021)
Abbvie	164.9 (MSN, n.d.-c)	39.4 (Abbvie, n.d.-b)	47,000 (Abbvie, n.d.-a)	2013 (Abbvie, n.d.-a), 8 years	Not involved
MSD	26.26 (MSN, n.d.-d.)	41.25 (MSD, n.d.-c)	74,000 (MSD, n.d.-b)	1891 (MSD, n.d.-a), 130 years	Not involved

Table 4. (continued)

Amgen	102.05 (MSN, n.d.-e)	21.8 (Amgen, 2021)	22,000 (Amgen, n.d.)	1980 (Amgen, n.d.), 41 years	Not involved
GSK	85.7 (MSN, n.d.-f)	40.3 (GSK, n.d.-a)	94,000 (GSK, n.d.-c)	2000 (GSK, n.d.-b), 21 years	Involved (Branswell, 2021)
Biogen	33.56 (MSN, n.d.-g)	13.4 (Biogen n.d.-a)	Could not be found	1978 (Biogen n.d.-b), 43 years	Not involved
BMS	110.1 (MSN, n.d.)	36.56 (BMS, 2021)	30,250 (macrotrends, n.d.-a)	1989 (BMS, n.d.), 32 years	Not involved
BioNTech	58 (MSN, n.d.)	1.2 (BioNTech, n.d.-a)	1,941 (macrotrends, n.d.-b)	2008 (BioNTech, n.d.-d), 13 years	Involved (BioNTech, n.d.-d)

Table 5. Twitter metrics.

GRP	No. of retweets per tweet	No. of likes per tweet	No. of received replies per tweet	No. of retweets made per day	No. of likes given to others per day	No. of replies made per day	Tweet frequency	No. of followers	Account age (in days)
Janssen	1.32	6.2	0.38	0.13	0.34	0.08	1.45	7020	2076
Fresenius	1.52	2.99	0.1	0.29	0.25	0.05	0.36	1429	4564
Daiichi Sankyo	1.24	8.15	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.003	0.29	9057	4554
Abbvie	1.57	4.54	0.08	0.25	1.28	0.04	1.12	6730	2216

Table 5. (continued)

MSD	2.28	9.7	0.24	0.01	0.54	0.03	0.33	3901	2308
Amgen	1.4	5.93	0.32	0.05	0.48	0.05	0.69	1662	1126
GSK	0.5	1.5	0.06	0.4	0.17	0.01	0.32	988	1805
Biogen	1.746	4.8	0.31	0.0006	0.021	0.012	0.38	210	325
BMS	1.44	6.17	0.3	0.1	0.34	0.01	0.33	1956	2301
BioNTech	46.83	201.08	13.43	0.026	0.02	0	0.13	57054	1004

Since the market capitalization of Janssen and the number of employees of Biogen had not been found, hypotheses with these variables were not tested.

4.3 Content analysis

The content analysis comprised two parts: A sentiment analysis of tweets by German Twitter users and a categorization of tweets by the sampled GRPs.

In the sentiment analysis, we assessed which kinds of sentiments users had expressed when tweeting about the pharmaceutical industry in general and when replying to tweets by GRPs collected in a sampling procedure described in section 4.3.4.

Both content analyses were done intellectually and did not rely on artificial intelligence tools to reduce the probability of misinterpreting nuances in the individual messages.

4.3.1 Collection and sampling of sentiment tweets

We initially hypothesized that the Covid-19 pandemic had affected the frequency of occurrence of tweets with negative sentiments towards the pharmaceutical industry. This was explored by a longitudinal approach in which tweets between 09/27/2019 and 08/15/21 were collected. All German tweets that expressed sentiments towards the pharmaceutical in that time-frame were defined as the population.

Four time-frames within the sampling frame were defined. The first time-frame contains tweets made after the WHO's first report of Covid-19 and before first public responses to the virus by GRPs on Twitter. The WHO report was made on 09/27/2019 (WHO, 2020b) and the first tweet by the sampled GRPs addressing the virus was posted on 02/27/20. Hence, the first time-frame ranges from 09/27/19 to 02/27/20. The next time-frame continues until 12/02/20 when the United Kingdom was the first country to authorize Covid-19 vaccines for public use (Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency, 2020). The third time-frame continues until 06/15/21 when the slow-down of the vaccine rollout was announced (Gye, 2021). The fourth time-frame continues until two months after the announced slow-down of the vaccine rollout (08/15/21).

To systematically identify pertinent hashtags and terms for the search query (i.e., data collection), an initial subset of 1,500 tweets containing the word "pharma" were collected with the standard Twitter API. The hashtags and words used in those tweets were assessed to determine whether they would be appropriate in the search query for the population. The following search terms were considered to be eligible:

- "pharma"
- "bigpharma"
- "pharmabranche"
- "pharmaindustrie"

The terms were separated by the “OR” operator and were entered once with hashtag and once without hashtag in the search query processed by the application “twarc2” which accessed the data through the academic Twitter API v2.

Notably, the search query found tweets of interest that did not use any of the terms specified above. Completely unrelated tweets were also collected. We decided to sample more tweets than necessary according to our sample size calculations because it was not known whether all tweets of interest were indeed collected by the search query.

A simple random sample from each of the defined time-frames was drawn and each tweet was treated as a unit of analysis. Equation 1 was used to calculate the sample sizes

Table 6. Sampling of sentiment tweets.

Time-frame	Population size (N)	Standard deviation (σ)	Required sample size (n)	Sampled tweets in addition to n
1	1,632	84.72	276	152
2	5,341	94.16	340	103
3	7,649	100.43	388	62
4	2,109	73.93	210	213

Since the proportions of the sentiments in the population were not known, the variability of the data was assessed by calculating the standard deviation of the number of likes. We considered a margin of error (e) of 10 units to be appropriate because the number of likes tweets can receive is only restricted to the number of users on Twitter and ranged up to 12,002 in the population.

We used the value 1.96 for Z which corresponds to a confidence interval of 95%.

Tweets were added to the required sample size such that each time-frame had a final sample size of at least 420 tweets. More tweets were added to certain time-frames if there was sufficient time to code them.

A simple random sample was drawn from each time-frame using the “randomize range” - functionality from Google Sheets.

4.3.2 Filtering

The unfiltered data consisted of 82,744 tweets. We first removed duplicate tweet author IDs such that each user could only appear once. This reduced the total number of tweets to 18,016. There were also several tweets unrelated to our subject. We first attempted to remove them manually from the population but realized that it was too time-consuming. We therefore only excluded them manually from the four samples by replacing them with randomly selected sentiment tweets. We also had to remove 1239 replies and 46 retweets that although it had been specified in the search query that such tweets should not be collected. The final population size was 16,731 tweets including an unknown number of tweets that did not express sentiments or were unrelated to this subject.

4.3.3 Sentiment analysis: Coding scheme

This part of our research was a conceptual replication of Hornikx & Hendrix (2015) who analyzed the sentiments of tweets towards consumer brands. They distinguished between negative, neutral, and positive sentiments.

In order to determine specific emotions behind positive and negative sentiments, we attempted to use Ekman’s (1987) six basic emotions which are commonly used as an emotion representation scheme (Wood et al., 2018). Since detecting emotions in text is a highly subjective task (Aman, 2007, p.36), the coders were provided with commonly shared definitions of those emotions (table 6) and a list of emotion indicators (Table 8 and 9) (i.e., words and emojis

that can be associated with certain emotions) to maximize intercoder agreement. However, there was a high level of disagreement in the test coding for this variable. We decided to omit this approach because briefing sessions and codebook calibrations did not seem to improve agreement. Our solution to this problem was to only distinguish between tweets that contained emotions and tweets that did not. The coders still used Ekman's emotion representation scheme and the indicators. Additionally, further indicators were developed inductively based on the patterns detected during the test-coding (see section 4.4.1).

Table 7. Sentiment analysis - initial coding scheme.

Sentiment	Emotion	Definition
Positive	Happiness	A state of well-being and contentment (Merriam-Webster, n.d.-a).
	Surprise	Feeling or showing surprise because of something unexpected (Merriam-Webster, n.d.-b).
Negative	Sadness	Affected with or expressive of grief or unhappiness (Merriam-Webster, n.d.-c).
	Fear	An unpleasant often strong emotion caused by anticipation or awareness of danger (Merriam-Webster, n.d.-d).

Table 7. (continued)

	Disgust	Marked aversion aroused by something highly distasteful (Merriam-Webster, n.d.-e).
	Anger	A strong feeling of displeasure and usually of antagonism (Merriam-Webster, n.d.-f).
	Surprise	Feeling or showing surprise because of something unexpected (Merriam-Webster, n.d.-b).
Neutral	No emotion	/

Table 8. Final coding scheme.

Sentiment	Emotions
Positive	Emotional/ Not emotional
Neutral	
Negative	

The variable “emotions” was not coded for in the sentiment analysis of replies to GRPs because this was not necessary for any of our hypotheses.

We relied again on a confidence interval of 95% but defined a smaller margin of error ($e = 2$ units) compared to the one used for sampling sentiment tweets because the impact scores had a smaller range (from 0 to 779). We sampled additional tweets for each GRP depending on how fast the content analysis progressed.

Table 11 Sample size for each GRP.

GRP	Population size (N)	Standard deviation (σ)	Required sample size (n)	Tweets sampled in addition to n
Janssen	447	7.87	60	147
Fresenius	194	7.34	52	79
Daiichi Sankyo	369	2.5	6	183
Abbvie	449	6.28	38	137
MSD	495	17.92	308	0
Amgen	306	5.87	33	140
GSK	220	2.8	8	138
Biogen	164	4.69	21	106
BMS	186	8.75	74	63
BioNTech	26	175.7	26 (Full-population sample)	/

4.3.5 Tweet categorization: Coding scheme

Park et al. (2016) and Neiger et al. (2013) who drew on Lovejoy & Saxton's (2012) three message functions distinguished between tweets about personal health topics and tweets about organizational matters. We took a similar approach by applying the message functions information and action to health contexts only, and by using Zhang et al's (2020) coding scheme to determine specific organizational topics in tweets. The definitions for the message functions "action" and "information" were taken from Han et al. (2019) who tailored them to a health-related context. For the message function "community", the original definition by Lovejoy & Saxton (2012) was used.

By including Edman's (2010) coding scheme, we wanted to assess whether GRPs preferred to use promotional or objective language. However, this coding scheme was slightly reduced: Indicators for replies and retweets were removed and we did not distinguish between symmetrical and asymmetrical two-way communication because this distinction was not useful for answering any of our hypotheses.

We also excluded the category "community relations" from Zhang et al.'s (2020) coding scheme because it was not describing organizational information, and it seemed to be identical to the message function "community".

The categories within a variable counted as mutually exclusive. If, however, multiple categories of one variable applied to a tweet, the more dominant one was selected.

Table 12. All tweet typology concepts used in the content analysis summarized.

Concept	Variable	Indicators
Communication model (Edman, 2010, pp.118-119)	Press agency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Persuasive language - One-way communication
	Public information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Objective communication of facts - One-way communication
	Two-way communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Feedback requests - Establishment of mutual understanding and building of long-term mutually beneficial relationships
Organizational topic (Zhang et al., 2020, pp.375-380)	Corporate social responsibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Displays activities that go beyond the company’s self interest (e.g., removing barriers for minorities, providing support for social equality and diversity, protecting the environment, etc.).”
	Research & Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Companies showcase their achievements in research and development.”
	Business insights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Companies share business-related knowledge (e.g., how to increase brand awareness, how to increase customer loyalty, etc.).”
	Partner relations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Tweets about companies’ alliances and collaborations with other parties.”

Table 12. (continued)

	Human resources	- "Provision of information about recruitment and corporate working environments and sharing employees' career experience."
	Government relations	- "Tweets that showcase the companies' public affairs efforts."
	Corporate achievements	- "Noteworthy achievements, such as being recognized as most reputable company or getting a high score on relevant rankings."
Message function (Lovejoy & Saxton, 2012; Han et al., 2019)	Information	- "Information about diseases, epidemics, educational programs, or general health information." (Han et al. 2019, p.427)
	Community	- "Foster relationships, create networks, and build communities on Twitter through tweets that promote interactivity and dialogue. The heart of this function are "dialogic" messages and those that attempt to build a community of followers via "bonding" messages, such as "thank you" and acknowledgement tweets." (Lovejoy & Saxton, 2012, p.343)

Table 12. (continued)

	Action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Encouraging users or followers to modify their lifestyle, maintain good health, take action to learn more about health, actively participate in conversation, and mobilize followers to adopt certain preventive measures or treatments.” (Han et al. 2019, p.427)
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4.4 Coding procedure

Tweet categorization:

Two coders were trained in test-coding sessions and de-briefings respectively. In the test-coding, 50 tweets from each GRP were analyzed. Coding sessions were revised if Krippendorff’s alpha was below 0.8 for a certain variable within each of the 10 samples. This was calculated in R using a package called “DescTools”. In total, 13 meetings to review the codes were arranged excluding those for the test-coding (one for each GRP and three additional ones to discuss general issues). The coding sheet of (J.B.) was used in the data analysis.

Table 13. Intercoder agreement for the tweet categorization ($n = 1662$).

Variable	Krippendorff’s alpha
Communication model	0.89
Organizational topic	0.9
Message function	0.92

The number of positive, neutral, and negative replies to those tweets was also captured. Full agreement was reached as tweets with replies were scarce. If tweets had replies, the number was usually low (i.e., below 3).

When drawing on the results of this content analysis, it should be taken into account that the agreement scores may be smaller for each individual GRP.

Sentiment analysis:

Two other individuals coded the sentiment tweets. As in the tweet categorization, they had to reach a Krippendorff's alpha value of at least 0.8 in the test- and final coding. The test-coding sample consisted of 100 tweets per time-frame. One meeting for each of the four time-frames was arranged to discuss disagreements. The coding sheet of (J.N.) was used in the data analysis.

Table 14. Inter-coder agreement values for the sentiment analysis (n = 1754).

Variable	Krippendorff's alpha
Sentiment	0.86
Emotion	0.84

Unfortunately, agreement scores as high as in the tweets categorization could not be reached in the given amount of time. It seems that more subjectivity is involved in this type of content analysis.

4.4.1 Codebook calibration

In this section it is described how the codebook was edited during the coding process.

Tweet categorization

In order to provide more clarity regarding the difference between press-agentry and public information, we added that press-agentry tweets aim at presenting the respective GRP in a good light and point out its societal value.

In the test-coding it became clear that Zhang et al.'s (2020) coding scheme could not explain all organization-related tweets. For example, some GRPs shared their history which did not fall into any of the existing categories. We therefore added the category "other" for tweets about organizational matters that could not be explained by Zhang et al.'s (2020) coding scheme.

Further minor adjustments to certain definitions were made. In the codebook, it can be seen which parts of each definition came from the original authors and which parts were added. This was mostly done to address misunderstandings and to make the definitions less specific.

Sentiment analysis

It had to be added that only sentiments towards the pharmaceutical industry should be analyzed because some tweets expressed sentiments towards multiple entities alongside the pharmaceutical industry such as insurance companies or governments. It was also necessary to specify that tweets pointing out the societal value of pharmaceutical companies should be counted as positive sentiment tweets. There were also several tweets that criticized unjustified accusations towards the pharmaceutical industry without directly expressing a positive sentiment. It was added that such tweets ought to be labeled as neutral.

Also, further emotion indicators were added based on the patterns detected inductively during the test-coding.

Table 15. Added emotion indicators.

Emotions	Added indicators
Emotional	- Excessive use of capital letters
	- Antagonism: Portraying the pharmaceutical industry as an enemy (e.g. pharma-mafia)
	- Excessive use of exclamation marks
	- Expressions of gratitude towards the pharmaceutical industry (happiness)
	- Insults
No emotions	Absence of emotion indicators

5.0 Results

To test hypotheses regarding the program-level impact of certain tweet types, we took two separate approaches.

First, we tested the hypotheses for each GRP individually. This approach was more robust against confounding variables affecting the number of likes and retweets of tweets. Although the analysis was thereby reduced to ten separate case-studies, we also attempted to find patterns across the results for all GRPs.

In the second approach, we used one sample incorporating all corporate tweets. While this approach was based on a larger, it was more vulnerable to confounding variables affecting the program-level performance of tweets. For example, certain GRPs might have more followers on Twitter because they receive more media coverage. Furthermore, certain GRPs employed the English language which may have given them a greater opportunity to reach more users and to thereby receive more endorsement. By conglomerating all tweets in the analysis, those differences were not accounted for. In hindsight, it may have been more appropriate to only analyze tweets by GRPs utilizing the German language as that would have reduced those differences.

To simplify the data analysis, an endorsement score for each tweet was calculated by adding the number of the received likes and retweets. All statistical tests were conducted with a 5% alpha level.

Corporate and sentiment tweets that could not be categorized due to ambiguity were excluded from the analysis.

5.1 Tweet categorization

H1: GRPs involved in Covid-19 vaccination research or development focus on different organizational topics compared to uninvolved GRPs.

A Chi-square test of independence was conducted comparing the communication behavior between GRPs involved ($n = 567$ tweets) and not involved ($n = 1096$ tweets) in Covid-19 vaccination research or development. A significant difference with a small effect size was found ($X^2(8, N = 1663) = 25.738, p = 0.001, \text{Cramer's } V = 0.124$).

In table 16 it is shown in percentages how frequently certain topics were addressed by each group.

Table 16. Organizational topics addressed by GRPs involved and not involved in Covid-19 vaccination research or development.

		Involved in Covid-19 vaccination research or development		Total
		No	Yes	
Organizational topic	Other	17.6%	20.3%	18.5%
	CSR	23.4%	18.9%	21.8%
	R&D	21.9%	26.4%	23.5%
	Business insights	11.1%	3.7%	8.5%
	Partner relations	11.8%	15.2%	13.0%
	Human resources	8.2%	9.7%	8.7%
	Corporate achievements	3.6%	4.3%	3.9%
	Government relations	2.5%	1.4%	2.1%
Total	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

Involved GRPs had a comparatively larger proportion of tweets addressing R&D. It was the most frequently addressed topic by involved GRPs and the second most addressed topic by uninvolved GRPs. The most frequently addressed topic by uninvolved GRPs was CSR which was the second most frequently addressed topic by involved GRPs (excluding the category “other”). The third most addressed topic (also excluding “other”) by both groups was partner relations although involved GRPs had a larger proportion of tweets dedicated to that topic. The most notable difference was that uninvolved GRPs shared business insights more than twice as frequently than involved GRPs. Both groups seemed to prioritize the topics human resources, corporate achievements, and government relations on a somewhat equal level. Since the differences between the two groups were significant, we considered the hypothesis to be verified.

H2: Tweets by GRPs containing organization-related information generally receive less endorsement than tweets not about organizational matters.

Approach 1 (splitted sample):

To determine which statistical test should be performed, the endorsement scores of the two tweet groups in each GRP were tested for normality. Histograms, Q-Q plots, and box plots were created to visually assess the normality of the data (this was the standard procedure to assess normality throughout this study). There was no case in which both tweet groups had normal distributions. We therefore conducted a Mann-Whitney U test of independence with endorsement as the dependent variable (as in all hypotheses with endorsement as a variable). The effect sizes were calculated with equation 2:

$$r = \left| \frac{z}{\sqrt{n}} \right|$$

Equation 2. Effect size calculation for Mann-Whitney U tests

A significant result was found for the GRPs Abbvie (U = 4703, p = 0.004, r = 0.254), Daiichi Sankyo (U = 3393.5, p = 0.006, r = 0.2), Janssen (U = 3646.5, p < 0.001, r = 0.23), and MSD (U = 7984, p < 0.001 r = 0.28).

Table 17. Mean ranks of endorsement for tweets with and without organizational information. Non-significant results are not shown.

Ranks

GRP_Name	Organizational topic	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Abbvie	Endorsement score No	115	98.90	11373.00
	Yes	105	123.21	12937.00
	Total	220		
Daiichi Sankyo	Endorsement score No	84	82.90	6963.50
	Yes	105	104.68	10991.50
	Total	189		
Janssen	Endorsement score No	80	86.08	6886.50
	Yes	126	114.56	14434.50
	Total	206		
MSD	Endorsement score No	143	127.83	18280.00
	Yes	165	177.61	29306.00
	Total	308		

In table 17, the larger mean rank within each GRP was color coded with green and the smaller one with red. This was done to facilitate detecting a pattern across the results of all GRPs.

The results indicate that organizational information in tweets lead to significantly higher levels of endorsement for each GRP listed in table 17.

Approach 2 (full sample):

Outliers were strongly present in the data. Although outliers affect the power of parametric as well as nonparametric tests, they reduce the power of the t-test to a greater extent compared to the Mann-Whitney U test (Zimmermann, 1994, p. 391). Therefore, we regarded the Mann-Whitney U test as more appropriate for this hypothesis. Also, the data was skewed rather than normally distributed.

The results show that tweets containing organization-related information (mean rank = 893.51, n = 987, 59.4%) yielded significantly higher endorsement levels: $U = 272894.5$, $p < 0.001$, when compared with tweets not containing such information (mean rank = 742.19, n = 676). This coincides with the results from the first approach with the splitted sample, which suggest that the hypothesis should be rejected. Also, it seems that there are more variables required to explain the endorsement scores of tweets as the effect size is small ($r = 0.155$).

H3: CSR and R&D are the most endorsed organizational topics by those who follow GRPs on Twitter.

Approach 1:

A Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted because the data was not normally distributed.

The GRPs that had significantly different endorsement scores between the eight topic categories (CSR, R&D, business insights, partner relations, human resources, corporate achievements, government relations, and other) were

Biogen ($H(7) = 22.897$, $p = 0.002$), BMS ($H(7) = 15.376$, $p = 0.018$), Daiichi Sankyo ($H(7) = 23.223$, $p = 0.002$), and Fresenius ($H(7) = 18.023$, $p = 0.012$).

Table 18. Mean ranks of endorsement for tweets with specific organizational topics. Non-significant results are not shown.

Ranks

GRP		Organizational topic	N	Mean Rank
Biogen	Endorsement score	Other	15	46.97
		CSR	21	19.64
		R&D	10	39.35
		Business insights	3	40.83
		Partner relations	8	27.81
		Human resources	5	32.90
		Corporate achievements	1	25.50
		Government relations	2	49.75
		Total	65	
BMS	Endorsement score	Other	7	39.21
		CSR	12	42.50
		R&D	18	33.69
		Business insights	15	49.10
		Partner relations	14	55.39
		Human resources	13	25.62
		Corporate achievements	3	55.67
		Total	82	
Daiichi Sankyo	Endorsement score	Other	26	45.69
		CSR	25	73.02
		R&D	6	40.92
		Business insights	10	66.30
		Partner relations	7	54.50
		Human resources	29	40.84
		Corporate achievements	1	4.50
		Government relations	1	72.50
		Total	105	
Fresenius	Endorsement score	Other	24	69.02
		CSR	11	42.50
		R&D	18	50.19
		Business insights	34	42.28
		Partner relations	3	65.50
		Human resources	7	69.93
		Corporate achievements	7	48.29
		Government relations	2	91.00
		Total	106	

This hypothesis was concerned with the two most endorsed organizational topics. The two topic categories with the highest mean ranks in each GRP were therefore color coded in green in table 18 (dark green: highest rank, light green: second highest rank).

The hypothesis could not be confirmed for any GRP. However, certain noteworthy patterns were detected. In the cases of Biogen, Daiichi Sankyo, and Fresenius, the topic category government relations lead to generally higher endorsement scores of tweets and was also one of the least frequently addressed topics. R&D consistently placed below fourth across all four GRPs

but was never the least endorsed topic. Endorsement the topic “CSR” varied strongly.

Approach 2:

The data was not normally distributed and a Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted. The results show a significant relationship between the organizational topics in tweets and the respective endorsement scores ($H(7) = 17.156$, $p = 0.016$).

The most endorsed and least frequently addressed topic category was government relations (mean rank = 678.93, $n = 21$) which is consistent with the pattern detected in the first approach. Despite being the most addressed topics in the sample (see figure 1), CSR (mean rank = 491.25, $n = 215$) and R&D (mean rank = 496.64, $n = 232$) were not the most endorsed organizational topics and placed sixth and fourth respectively. The hypothesis could therefore not be verified.

Figure 1. Relative occurrence of tweets with specific organizational topics.

H4: Tweets about CSR generally receive more positive replies when compared with tweets containing other organizational topics.

Approach 1:

The data was not normally distributed and Kruskal-Wallis tests were conducted. The results show that only MSD had a significant relationship between the topic categories and the respective number of received positive replies ($H(7) = 18.149$, $p = 0.011$). Tweets containing information related to corporate achievements (mean rank = 97.9, $n = 5$) and human resources (mean rank = 89.09, $n = 11$) received the highest amount of positive replies. The topics CSR (mean rank = 81.5, $n = 47$) and R&D (mean rank = 81.5, $n = 24$) placed fourth each.

Approach 2:

A Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted because the data was not normally distributed. A significant relationship between the topic categories and the number of received positive replies was found ($H(7) = 17.113$, $p = 0.017$). The results show that the topic category corporate achievements received the highest number of positive replies (mean rank = 558.09, $n = 38$) followed by R&D (mean rank = 501.23, $n = 232$) and CSR (mean rank = 494.16, $n = 215$).

The results from both approaches suggest that the hypothesis should be rejected.

H5: GRPs predominantly communicate about health by disseminating information.

Approach 1:

The message functions information and action were only applied to health information in the content analysis. Each GRP focused mostly on disseminating health information. Health-action tweets were usually sent the least frequently

(see table 19). The sample of BioNTech had no action-tweets. In table 19, the color green marks the largest percentage within each GRP. Yellow marks the second highest and red the lowest percentage.

Table 19. Percentage and frequency of information-, community-, and action-tweets within each GRP.

GRP			Frequency	Percent
Abbvie	Valid	Information	140	87.0
		Community	13	8.1
		Action	8	5.0
		Total	161	100.0
Amgen	Valid	Information	101	85.6
		Community	14	11.9
		Action	3	2.5
		Total	118	100.0
Biogen	Valid	Information	73	83.9
		Community	10	11.5
		Action	4	4.6
		Total	87	100.0
Biontech	Valid	Information	9	81.8
		Community	2	18.2
		Total	11	100.0
BMS	Valid	Information	62	87.3
		Community	8	11.3
		Action	1	1.4
		Total	71	100.0
Daiichi Sankyo	Valid	Information	68	59.6
		Community	29	25.4
		Action	17	14.9
		Total	114	100.0
Fresenius	Valid	Information	38	74.5
		Community	11	21.6
		Action	2	3.9
		Total	51	100.0
GSK	Valid	Information	89	91.8
		Community	3	3.1
		Action	5	5.2
		Total	97	100.0
Janssen	Valid	Information	124	80.0
		Community	24	15.5
		Action	7	4.5
		Total	155	100.0
MSD	Valid	Information	140	71.4
		Community	31	15.8
		Action	25	12.8
		Total	196	100.0

Approach 2:

Figure 2 confirms the finding from the first approach, namely that information was the most widely used message function.

Figure 2. Relative occurrence of information-, community-, and action-tweets.

The results seem to verify the hypothesis.

H6: Tweets that encourage health-improving actions generally receive more endorsement than tweets that disseminate health information.

Approach 1:

Kruskal-Wallis tests were conducted because the data was not normally distributed. A significant relationship between the message function and the endorsement score of tweets could only be detected in the sample of Biogen ($H(2) = 6.204$, $p = 0.045$). The message function “community” (mean rank = 58.7, $n = 10$) received the most endorsement. Tweets that disseminated health information (mean rank = 43.12, $n = 73$) scored second and tweets that encouraged health-improving actions scored last (mean rank = 23.38, $n = 4$).

Approach 2:

No significant relationship between the message functions and endorsement scores of tweets was found: $H(2) = 0.752$, $p = 0.687$. Figure 3 illustrates that the three message functions received somewhat similar levels of endorsement.

Figure 3. Box plots representing endorsement for each message function.

Not all outliers are shown in Figure 3 to maintain the legibility of the box plots (the size of the y-axis was reduced from 700 to 30). The results suggest that the hypothesis should be rejected.

H7: Objective communication by GRPs resonates more strongly with their Twitter followers rather than self-promotional tweets.

Approach 1:

Kruskal-Wallis tests were conducted because the data was not normally distributed.

A significant relationship between the communication models and the endorsement scores of tweets was detected in the samples from Biogen ($H(2)$

= 6.181, $p = 0.045$), Abbvie ($H(2) = 9.568$, $p = 0.008$), Daiichi Sankyo ($H(2) = 6.135$, $p = 0.047$), Fresenius ($H(2) = 6.335$, $p = 0.042$), Janssen ($H(2) = 6.797$, $p = 0.033$), and MSD ($H(2) = 7.394$, $p = 0.025$). The relative ranking of the communication models in each GRP are shown below in table 20.

Table 20. Mean ranks for endorsement of tweets with communication models. Only significant results are shown.

GRP_Name	Communication_model	N	Mean Rank
Abbvie	Press agency	62	131.01
	Public information	150	101.61
	Two-way communication	8	118.31
	Total	220	
Biogen	Press agency	36	52.67
	Public information	85	67.29
	Two-way communication	6	85.42
	Total	127	
Daiichi Sankyo	Press agency	74	105.06
	Public information	92	84.51
	Two-way communication	20	92.08
	Total	186	
Fresenius	Press agency	74	60.89
	Public information	46	65.96
	Two-way communication	9	93.89
	Total	129	
Janssen	Press agency	71	116.77
	Public information	127	98.03
	Two-way communication	8	72.56
	Total	206	
MSD	Press agency	107	171.46
	Public information	167	141.99
	Two-way communication	31	148.58
	Total	305	

In four out of all six cases, press agency was the highest scoring model. Also, Biogen and Fresenius had the same rank order. The model “two-way communication” was used the least by each GRP.

Approach 2:

In the second approach we also conducted a Kruskal-Wallis test because the data was not normally distributed. The result shows that there was a significant relationship between the communication models and the endorsement scores of tweets: $H(2) = 9.789$, $p = 0.007$. Two-way communication was the highest scoring and least frequently used model (mean rank = 889.67, $n = 96$ (5.8%)). Public information was the lowest scoring and most frequently used model (mean rank = 791.8, $n = 926$ (56.3%)). The model “press agency” (mean rank = 860.37, $n = 624$ (37.9%)) scored second.

Since tweets with the press agency model received on average significantly more endorsement than tweets with a public information model, the hypothesis should be rejected.

Figure 4. Box plots representing endorsement for each communication model.

In Figure 4, the size of the y-axis was reduced from 800 to 30.

H8: Tweets with a two-way communication model are correlated with a higher number of replies compared to tweets with the communication models “press agency” and “public information”.

Approach 1:

Kruskal-Wallis tests were conducted because the data was not normally distributed. The results show a significant relationship between the communication model of tweets and the number of replies for Amgen ($H(2) = 13.849$, $p < 0.001$) and MSD ($H(2) = 7.082$, $p = 0.029$).

Table 21. Mean ranks of replies to tweets with certain communication models.

Ranks

GRP_Name	Communication_model	N	Mean Rank
Amgen	Replies		
	Press agency	58	78.61
	Public information	102	86.76
	Two-way communication	11	117.91
	Total	171	
MSD	Replies		
	Press agency	107	143.30
	Public information	167	159.92
	Two-way communication	31	149.18
	Total	305	

Table 21 shows that press agency tweets generally lead to less replies in both cases. The hypothesis could only be verified for Amgen.

Approach 2

The result from the second approach indicates that there was no significant relationship between the number of replies and the communication model of tweets: $H(2) = 0.981$, $p = 0.640$.

Figure 5 shows that the majority of the tweets from GRPs had zero replies (86.2%). The insignificant result could therefore be a consequence of the low

number of users willing to interact with GRPs on Twitter regardless of the communication model of their tweets, and not because of an insufficient sample size.

Figure 5. Histogram showing the number of tweets that have a certain number of replies.

The size of the x-axis in Figure 5 was reduced from 50 to 5.

H9: Tweets about R&D are the most controversial (indicated by the number of negative replies).

Approach 1:

A Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted because the data was not normally distributed. A near-significant relationship between the topic categories and the number of negative replies was found for MSD: $H(7) = 14.000$, $p = 0.051$. All topics except for human resources (mean rank = 90) had a mean rank of 82.5.

Approach 2:

Following the second approach, there was no significant relationship between the organizational topic categories and the number of negative replies: $H(7) = 12.318$, $p = 0.091$.

5.2 Structural analysis

H10: GRPs that are more interactive on Twitter are more likely to receive endorsement from other users.

To understand the relationship between interactivity and endorsement, we first calculated an interactivity score for each GRP with the following formula:

$$\text{Interactivity} = 2 * \text{Replies (given)} + \text{Likes (given)} + \text{Retweets (given)}$$

The interactivity score was determined by the average number of replies made per day, the average number of likes given to others per day, and the average number of retweets made per day. The average number of replies made per day was weighted by a factor of 2 because we considered it to be a significantly stronger indicator of interactivity.

This hypothesis was tested with Spearman's rank-order correlation due to the low number of data entries. The result showed no difference in outcome ($\rho = -0.45$, $p = 0.192$).

H11: GRPs that are financially more successful (measured by their financial turnover in 2020) are more likely to be more active on Twitter (measured by their tweet frequencies).

Spearman's rank-order correlation showed no difference in outcome ($\rho = 0,049$ $p = 0.894$).

H12: GRPs that are less active on Twitter (measured by their tweet frequencies) are more likely to have less followers.

Spearman's rank-order correlation showed no difference in outcome ($\rho = -0.231$, $p = 0.521$).

H13: Older GRPs (measured by their age since foundation) are more likely to have a higher number of followers on Twitter.

Spearman's rank-order correlation showed no difference in outcome ($\rho = -0.406$, $p = 0.244$).

5.3 Sentiment analysis

H14: The number of tweets with positive sentiments increased after the UK authorized Covid-19 vaccines for public use.

We first created a frequency table and compared the time-frames 2 (prior to the vaccine authorization) and 3 (after the vaccine authorization). Table 22 shows that the frequency of occurrence of positive sentiment tweets decreased by 60% (from 15 to 9). Also, the proportion of negative sentiment tweets in the third time-frame is larger.

Table 22. Occurrence of sentiment tweets in the four time-frames.

		Sentiment			Total
		Positive	Neutral	Negative	
Timeframe 1	Count	18	123	246	387
	% within Timeframe	4.7%	31.8%	63.6%	100.0%
2	Count	15	177	202	394
	% within Timeframe	3.8%	44.9%	51.3%	100.0%
3	Count	9	143	279	431
	% within Timeframe	2.1%	33.2%	64.7%	100.0%
4	Count	12	93	288	393
	% within Timeframe	3.1%	23.7%	73.3%	100.0%
Total	Count	54	536	1015	1605
	% within Timeframe	3.4%	33.4%	63.2%	100.0%

To assess the significance of the results, a chi-square test of independence was conducted comparing the sentiments across the four time-frames. A significant interaction with a weak effect size was found ($\chi^2(6, N = 1605) = 46.819$, $p < .001$, Cramer's $V = 0.121$).

The results suggest that the hypothesis should be rejected.

H15: The number of tweets with negative sentiments increased after the announcement of the slow-down of the vaccine rollout.

The fourth time-frame contains all tweets posted after the announcement of the slow-down. Table 22 indicates that this time-frame had the highest proportion of negative sentiment tweets compared to the other time-frames ($\chi^2(6, N = 1605) = 46.819, p < .001, \text{Cramer's } V = 0.121$). This result suggests that the null hypothesis should be rejected.

H16: Tweets with negative sentiments towards the pharmaceutical industry were more likely to be emotional when compared to neutral and positive sentiments.

A chi-square analysis of independence was conducted to determine the significance of the relationship between the three sentiments and presence of emotions in tweets. The result indicates a significant interaction with a small to medium effect size ($\chi^2(2, N = 1596) = 217.092, p < 0.001, \text{Cramer's } V = 0.369$). Table 23 indicates that most negative sentiment tweets were not emotional (59%).

Table 23. Cross-tabulation of the variables “sentiment” and “emotions”.

		Emotions		Total	
		Emotional	Not emotional		
Sentiment	Positive	Count	26	28	54
		% within Sentiment	48.1%	51.9%	100.0%
	Neutral	Count	31	505	536
		% within Sentiment	5.8%	94.2%	100.0%
	Negative	Count	411	595	1006
		% within Sentiment	40.9%	59.1%	100.0%
Total	Count	468	1128	1596	
	% within Sentiment	29.3%	70.7%	100.0%	

This result suggests that the hypothesis should be rejected. However, it should also be mentioned that 87.8% of all emotional tweets had a negative sentiment. If the hypothesis had been phrased differently (e.g., “emotional tweets are more likely to have a negative sentiment”), we were able to reject the null hypothesis.

H17: The number of positive sentiment tweets increased after the declaration of the pandemic.

A chi-square test of independence was conducted to assess whether the proportions of the three sentiments significantly changed after the onset of the pandemic. On 04/11/2020 the WHO officially declared the Covid-19 outbreak a pandemic (WHO 2020). The result indicates that the proportions of the sentiments did not significantly differ after the beginning of the pandemic: ($X^2(2, N = 1605) = 2.691, p = 0.26$).

H18: Positive sentiment tweets received more endorsement compared to neutral and negative sentiment tweets.

Due to extreme outliers and a non-normal distribution of the data, a Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted. The result indicates that the sentiment of a tweet seemed to determine how much endorsement it received: $H(2) = 22.544, p < 0.001$.

Table 24 indicates that positive sentiments expressed in tweets generally lead to more endorsement, and that negative sentiment tweets generally lead to less endorsement.

Table 24. Mean ranks of endorsement for sentiment tweets.

	Sentiment	N	Mean Rank
Endorsement	Positive	54	954.21
	Neutral	536	858.06
	Negative	1015	765.88
	Total	1605	

Figure 6. Box plots displaying endorsement for each sentiment.

The size of the y-axis was reduced from 25000 to 30 in figure 6. The full view made the box plots illegible but showed that there were more outliers for the neutral and negative sentiment. The results seem to verify the hypothesis.

6.0 Discussion

We investigated the organizational use of Twitter by GRPs (tweet categorization), the sentiments of German Twitter users towards the broader

pharmaceutical industry (sentiment analysis), and correlations between structural characteristics and Twitter metrics of GRPs (structural analysis). Each of those three analyses were based on the three research questions below. The results of this study have a reduced level of generalizability because only non-parametric tests were conducted.

RQ1: What types of tweets are sent how frequently by GRPs, with which impact on the program level?

The tweet categorization was conducted to assess which communication approaches and topics were prioritized by GRPs on Twitter, and to assess the program-level impact of different types of tweets. Two approaches were taken to test hypotheses related to RQ1: (1) a splitted-sample approach in which each GRP was analyzed individually and (2) a full-sample approach in which all tweets were analyzed at once.

In the content analysis, tweets were put into two broad categories - that is, tweets that share organizational information and tweets that share general health information. In the full sample, most tweets had an organization-related topic (59.4%) and generally received significantly more endorsement than tweets without organizational information ($p < 0.001$). This result coincides with the findings from the splitted-sample approach. The public health agencies analyzed by Park et al. (2016) also mostly shared information about organizational matters (67.7%). Conversely, the local health departments analyzed by Neiger et al. (2013) had a lower proportion of organizational tweets (39.5%). Our result suggests that individuals follow GRPs not mainly because they are providers of health information, but primarily because they are interested in following organizational developments. Unfortunately, it is not clear what types of individuals liked and retweeted which types of tweets because those who endorsed them were simplified to a homogeneous group of users in our analysis. For example, investors or employees of certain GRPs might have endorsed different tweet types compared to unaffiliated individuals. The other cited studies also did not make that differentiation, probably because

it would have been too difficult or even not feasible to categorize each user who liked a tweet, especially if those tweets had large numbers of likes and retweets. Furthermore, Twitter users may provide too little information about themselves to be appropriately categorized.

The organizational topics R&D (23.51%) and CSR (21.78%) were addressed the most frequently in the full sample. However, they did not receive comparatively high levels of endorsement ($p = 0.016$). The topic government relations (2.13%) was endorsed the most, but was also the least frequently addressed one, perhaps because GRPs want avoid revealing potentially sensitive information. Notably, Zhang et al. (2020) who developed the organizational topic categories had similar results when they analyzed tweets by large information technology companies: R&D and CSR were the most addressed topics (excluding community relations), and government relations was the least addressed topic. Unfortunately, a substantial proportion of tweets with an organizational topic were assigned to the category “other” (18.54%) during the coding process. This indicates that important topic categories were missing in the codebook. In hindsight, the deductive coding procedure should have been complemented with an inductive approach to determine those missing topic categories. The following categories could have been developed:

- Corporate vision and values:

GRPs communicate their values and share how they want to impact society.

- Communication efforts:

GRPs mention their efforts of raising awareness for certain diseases.

- Corporate events:

Mentioning of events organized by the respective GRP

- Nominations:

GRPs nominate scientists or organizations.

- Leadership:

GRPs share information about their executives.

- Corporate history:

GRPs share information about their past.

However, these categories are only suggestions as there was no formal coding procedure conducted to develop them.

Several scholars argued that participation and dialogue constituted key components of organizational social media communication (e.g., Bunting & Lipski, 2000; Gruber, 2008; Jones et al., 2009). Notably, the results show that two-way communication tweets generally received more endorsement than press agency and public information tweets ($p = 0.007$). However, in the full sample, only 5.8% were labelled as two-way communication tweets. Hence, GRPs could generate higher program-level impact on Twitter by sending more two-way communication tweets. Also Park et al. (2016) concluded that health organizations could optimize their use of Twitter by further embracing dialogic formats. We initially hypothesized that public information tweets received more endorsement than press agency tweets. But despite being the most prevalent in the full sample (56.3%), public information tweets generally received on less endorsement than press agency tweets (37.9%).

The majority of tweets in the full sample had no replies (86.2%). Since the body of literature regards interaction with stakeholders on social media as pivotal (e.g., Lovejoy & Saxton, 2012; Park et al., 2016; Neiger et al., 2013), the lack of replies to GRPs can be regarded as an issue. Moreover, Jones (2009) said community participation and collaboration in social web environments were key

for effective online reputation management (p. 936). Following that statement, GRPs should not expect that their current use of Twitter will lead to significant improvements in reputation. It may seem logical to conclude that more two-way communication tweets would increase the chances of receiving replies by other users. However, the results of this study indicate no relationship between the communication model of tweets and the number of received replies. Perhaps, a qualitative investigation (e.g., through survey or interviews) of followers of GRPs may lead to insights about what impedes them from engaging in discussions.

The three message functions developed by Lovejoy & Saxton (2012) were also applied in the tweet categorization. The message functions “information” and “action” were only applied to health contexts. In the full sample, information tweets (79.55%) were much more present than community (13.67%) and action tweets (6.79%). Park et al. (2016) reported similar results: their full sample contained 464 information-tweets and only 46 action-tweets about personal health. Also the local health departments analyzed by Neiger (2013) mostly sent information tweets (58.5%) to communicate health-related information. However, our findings regarding the program-level impact of tweets with different message functions is different compared to Park et al. (2016). They found that the message function of a tweet influenced the likelihood of being liked ($p < 0.001$). This relationship was not found in our full sample.

The tweet categorization had two further limitations: First, the samples were only representative of the tweets made since 04/13/2021. However, this could be seen as an opportunity to analyze tweets made before that date to assess whether the communication behavior of GRPs changed over time. Secondly, users on Twitter can pay to promote their own tweets. This increases the chances of such tweets to receive replies and endorsement, as more users get exposed to them. It is not clear how many likes, retweets, or replies were given to the sampled tweets due to promotion.

RQ2: Which sentiments toward the broader pharmaceutical industry and individual GRPs can be deduced from the views expressed by German Twitter users?

The results from the sentiment analysis suggest that the pharmaceutical industry is a highly controversial topic on Twitter: 63.2% of the sentiment tweets were negative and only 3.4% were positive. Also, 40.9% of all negative sentiment tweets were emotional which may make it particularly challenging to resolve those conflicts. This could be a consequence of the anti-corporate culture on the internet as discussed by Bunting & Lipski, (2000). However, in the study by Hornikx & Hendriks (2015), the overall proportion of negative sentiment tweets constituted less than half of the sample ($n = 282$, 44%). This suggests that there may be reasons beyond general corporate hostility on the net for the large proportion of negative sentiment tweets in our sample. Further work would be required to investigate why those users expressed negative sentiments. This could be explored in an inductive content in which categories of criticism would be assigned to the negative sentiment tweets.

However, it should be taken into consideration that this result does not represent all German Twitter users. It only represents those users who were willing to send a tweet with regard to this topic. In fact, we found that positive sentiment tweets seemed to receive on average more endorsement than neutral and negative sentiment tweets ($p < 0.001$). One could speculate that those who have a positive attitude towards pharmaceutical companies are more silent on Twitter and mostly endorse tweets from other users rather than sending their own tweets. It should be noted, however, that there was a large number of endorsement scores of tweets that counted as outliers. This was probably the case because the number of followers of each tweet author was a variable that was not controlled for. This should be taken into account in future studies because users with a large number of followers can reach more people on Twitter and have therefore higher chances of receiving more likes and retweets.

Furthermore, the intensity of the sentiment tweets was not evaluated. Hence, it is not clear whether the tweets were made because of a temporary state of the authors, or because of their general attitude towards the pharmaceutical industry. The intensity of sentiment tweets could be quantified in a content analysis with e.g., a Likert scale. However, it would probably be challenging to reach high agreement values for such a variable.

Also, although the differences between the four time-frames were statistically significant, it seems unlikely that the events separating the four time-frames were the only causes for the changes in the relative proportions of the sentiments, and it is also not clear whether those were causal relationship in the first place.

RQ3: How do certain structural characteristics of GRPs correlate with their metrics, impacts, and communication behavior on Twitter?

Significant correlations between Twitter metrics and structural characteristics of GRPs were not found. Also Costa et al (2018) did not find associations between the engagement scores for any of the analyzed platforms and structural characteristics of the pharmaceutical companies. However, we also juxtaposed the structural characteristic “involvement in Covid-19 vaccination research or development” with the organizational topic categories. A significant difference between involved and uninvolved GRPs was found ($p = 0.001$). This result suggests that GRPs base their social media agenda on certain circumstances. By conducting content analyses of strategic social media communication documents from GRPs, this hypothesis could be tested in greater detail.

7.0 Conclusion

The communication of GRPs on Twitter is characterized by information dissemination and one-way messages. Their tweets rarely lead to discussions with other users, which indicates that Twitter is not optimally used. Moreover,

the pharmaceutical industry is a controversial topic on German Twitter and resolving those conflicts may be challenging in particular due to a substantial number of emotionally involved critics.

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Johannes Bopp